

Effect of nutrition behavior change communication on Nutrition Knowledge and dietary practices of pregnant adolescents in West Arsi, Central Ethiopia: a cluster randomized controlled trial

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study investigated the effect of communication about nutritional behavior 13 changes on the nutritional knowledge and dietary practices of pregnant adolescents in the West 14 Arsi Zone, Central Ethiopia.

Design: A two-arm parallel cluster randomized controlled community trial was carried out.

Settings: West Arsi zone, Central Ethiopia.

Intervention: A Nutritional behavioral change communication (NBCC) intervention based on the health belief model (HBM) was administered via Alliance for Development (AFD) starting at 16 weeks of gestation. The intervention included food preparation demonstrations and pregnant adolescents and their husbands attending the NBCC.

Participants: A total of 207 and 219 pregnant adolescents were included in 14 clusters in the intervention group and another 14 clusters in the control group, respectively.

Primary and secondary outcomes: Dietary practice was the primary outcome, and nutritional knowledge was the secondary outcome.

Methods: This study was conducted from August 2022 to July 2023. Each pregnant adolescent in the intervention group attended four counseling sessions. Adolescents in the control group attended the routine nutritional counseling provided by the health care system. Generalized estimating equations were used to evaluate the effect of the intervention. Difference-in-differences was employed to estimate the net treatment effect.

Results: The appropriate dietary practice rate increased by 20.3 percentage points in the intervention group and decreased by 5.6 percentage points in the control group. After controlling for possible confounders, the odds of appropriate dietary practices increased by 13% in the comparison group [AOR=1.13; 95% CI=1.02, 1.2], and pregnant adolescents in the intervention group had an AOR which was 3.7 times that of the comparison group in appropriate dietary practices [AOR =4.2, 95% CI=2.6, 5.3]. The odds of good nutritional knowledge increased in both groups, however, the NBCC group had an increase 5.5 times (95%CI: 3.8, 8.1) that of the comparison group.

Conclusions: NBCC through AFDs based on the HBM is an effective approach for increasing the proportion of pregnant adolescents who practice appropriately and have good nutritional knowledge.

Key words: Pregnant adolescent, Alliance for development, Nutritional Behavior Change Communication

Clinical trial registration: PACTR202203696996305, Pan African Clinical Trials Registry

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